

**MODERN APPROACHES AND PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN
TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES AS A MEANS OF DEVELOPING
CRITICAL THINKING.**

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Annotation

The article describes the use of the technology of critical thinking development in English lessons. The examples of how to apply techniques of this technology are given. The positive aspects of this technology and the difficulties in using the technology of critical thinking development are presented.

Keywords: individual culture, systematization of information, collective performance, differentiated approach.

According to Uzbekistan educational standards the formation of critical thinking is one of the most important universal competencies. This shows that educators have fully realized the importance of developing critical thinking for many years of educational practice, but in the question of how to develop critical thinking, in particular when teaching a foreign language, researchers still have a long way to go. Traditional foreign language teaching cannot provide an answer to this problem due to its outdated theories and monotonous methods. It only requires the use of materials to learn the language expression and mechanical memorization, instead of asking pupils to think about the materials themselves. Thus, it is impossible to develop critical thinking, sometimes even the cognitive thinking activity of pupils is destroyed.[1, p 7]

Chinese scholars believe that the development of pupils' critical thinking can occur when implementing any subject. Nevertheless, the emphasis on the development of critical thinking in teaching foreign languages is made because, firstly, there is a natural connection between language and the ability to think; secondly, learning a foreign language opens a window to students in different cultures, and these differences between cultures are the best materials for stimulating critical thinking. Having studied foreign theories, scientists, experts in the development of critical thinking in teaching foreign languages, Wen Qiufang and Sun Min proposed to divide critical thinking into three main skills: analysis, inference and evaluation . Subsequently, on the basis of empirical research conducted in classes on foreign languages (English, Russian and German) in some of China's leading schools, they have further decomposed three core skills on a variety of secondary skills for ease of teaching. Secondary skills under "analysis" include interpretation, classification, comparison and identification; "inference" includes a collection of evidence, an offer of alternatives, a conclusion and an explanation; and "evaluation" is divided into arguments and self-regulation. [1, p 9]

In addition, according to Wen Qiufang, in terms of the form of teaching foreign language in order to develop critical thinking, there are two modes: conscious and unconscious. In a conscious mode, the teacher clearly informs the students and explains what kind of pedagogical activity they are engaged in. Pupils are well aware that they and at the same time are learning subject matter by thinking. In an unconscious mode, the teacher hides his or her pedagogical goal, does not introduce pupils the concept of critical thinking and will not touch on relevant knowledge and concepts in the classroom critical thinking, but allows pupils to form the skills of critical thinking skills through well-designed tasks and questions, to better integrate critical thinking instruction into foreign language teaching and alleviate the difficulties caused by conceptual abstraction. It can be said that in this mode, pupils do not form a mindset, they just train to think critically on a foreign language. The choice of mode mainly depends on the age and cognitive level of pupils. For pupils, the conscious mode is

more effective due to the fact that it promotes development in pupils self-reflection and self-control skills.[1, p8]

As for the features of pedagogical technologies, these are the principles of using technology. While technology is rapidly updated, principles rarely change. Kulamikhina I.V. and Yesmurzayeva Zh.B. identified four principles that necessarily correspond to the teaching technology foreign languages in order to develop critical thinking:

1) meaningful study of a foreign language. Modern researchers emphasize that teaching communication in a foreign language should not only include cognitive aspects, but also draw great attention to them so that pupils can successfully master language and communication skills.[1,30]

2) personal activity in learning. Generation and understanding of meaning makes pupils more motivated and more active in learning and thinking;

3) collaborative learning. The goal of learning together is not so much to master knowledge as it is to learn how to learn with others. Thanks to this, pupils can gain skills socialization, communication and critical thinking skills;

4) the use of support stimuli in teaching [2, p.230]. According to Vygotsky L.S., the development of thinking is mediated process, that is, for the development of any mental function (analysis, synthesis, evaluation) it is necessary to create a sign or symbol that will become a support or stimulus for the individual to master or development of knowledge, skills, abilities. Support-stimulus can act as a subject of collectively distributed activities of pupils.[3, p 207]

The methodological peculiarity could be the activation of students' independent work in the classroom and afterwards. Independent work stimulates interest in research, and pupils are more willing to take the initiative to learn, so that the motivation to learn becomes higher. With a strong motivation to learn, pupils stop working negligently, and learn the materials more deeply. Having studied the materials,

impressions of the materials give them the desire to create and take the initiative. [4, p.207].

Thanks to the rapid development of information technology, pupils can now easily engage in independent work. And it is worth noting that this does not contradict the principle of learning in cooperation when choosing modern pedagogical technologies, because cooperation requires each member to fulfill his part and make his own contribution, regardless of the form in which cooperation is carried out.

The pedagogical feature is that the development of critical thinking in teaching a foreign language should always be closely related to professionalism due to the fact that, ultimately, the priority goal of modern education is to train a qualified and competent worker [5, p.72]. This feature is reflected in the training by the fact that the development of tasks can not be limited to solving problems in everyday life, but also allows pupils to try to solve problems that may arise in future professional life. This will greatly benefit their future career realization.

Another pedagogical feature is the deep integration of critical thinking skills and communicative abilities. Thinking is the understanding and generation of meaning, and communication is the encoding and decoding of meaning. [6, p.40]. From this point of view, thinking and communication have deep connections, which is the basis for the simultaneous development of these two complications.

In the course of training pupils should be given as many opportunities as possible to speak. When they need to speak, they may have problems such as illegible words, confusing words, ambiguity, evasiveness, innuendo, verbosity, digressions, lack of logic, lack of arguments, etc. In this case, the teacher can help students clarify their thoughts through questions. In this process, pupils can understand what their problem is more related to, thinking or expression, and then perform targeted exercises to improve their respective abilities. At the same time, the teacher can invite previous pupils to answer questions in order to simultaneously train their listening and understanding skills. For example, according to the model developed by previous

researchers, there are such types of tasks as "know - want to know - learn", "forecasting from photography" and "synchwain" [7,p 19], which require meaningful and thoughtful expressions from pupils and therefore can be used to combine the development of critical thinking skills and communicative competence. When a teacher selects materials for discussion and teaching critical thinking, he should apply the following principles:

1) the principle of analysis and generalization of the material. The materials chosen

cannot be too simple. Pupils must reflect and analyze in order to understand the materials;

2) the principle of problemativeness. Problems with openness (that is, there is more than one correct answer to such a problem.) can stimulate critical thinking;

3) the principle of interdisciplinarity. The principle of interdisciplinarity allows pupils to look at the same problem from different perspectives. Comparing and analyzing the differences in these views, pupils develop critical thinking skills;

4) materials with complexity and fuzziness. The judgments that pupils encounter every day are not clear and completely correct. Often seemingly fair judgments contain the implied premises, position, bias and prejudice of the author. Critical thinking skills require students to be identified;

5) materials that defy common sense. The practical feature of teaching critical thinking is the phasing of implementation.

Since Bloom, educators have considered the development of critical thinking as a step-by-step process. The most widely used at present is the classification of the technology of development of critical thinking, which divides the entire process into three phases: challenge - comprehension - reflection.

There are different tasks at each stage.

The task of the challenge stage is usually to introduce students to the discussion of the topic with the help of some questions related to everyday life, activating the

existing knowledge and experiences of pupils; the comprehension stage is basically the stage of studying new materials. At this stage, the teacher should comprehensively use various tasks to make sure that pupils have already deeply understood the materials; in the reflection stage, pupils must integrate the old and new knowledge gained in the first and second stages in order to make their own findings.

Now many specific and effective methodological techniques used at each stage have already been developed. For example, at the call stage, the techniques "cluster", "associations" and "prediction", etc. can be used; at the stage of comprehension there are techniques "mental map", "fish bone", "six hats", "brainstorm", "insert", "subtle" and "interpreting" questions, etc. ; and at the stage of reflection - the techniques of "discussion", "essay" and "contrastive table of conclusions", etc. [8, 22].

In accordance with different situations, these techniques can be introduced into other pedagogical technologies for teaching foreign language in order to develop critical thinking. So, after studying the literature of scientists from China ,Russia and Uzbekistan on the development of critical thinking in teaching foreign language, we concluded that the development of critical thinking in teaching foreign language has rationality. There are two modes of development of critical thinking when teaching foreign language: conscious and unconscious.

For pupils, the conscious mode is more effective. When choosing modern pedagogical technologies for the development of critical thinking in teaching foreign language, it is necessary to be guided by four principles:

- meaningful learning of a foreign language;
- the activity of the individual in learning;
- training in cooperation;
- the use of supports-incentives in learning.

In addition, a methodological feature of the development of critical thinking in teaching foreign language is the activation of independent work; Pedagogical features

are professionalism and integration skills of critical thinking and communicative abilities;

The technology of critical thinking is used in foreign language lessons and allows you to significantly increase the time of speech practice in the lesson for each student, to achieve the assimilation of the material by all group members, to solve a variety of educational and developmental tasks. The teacher, in turn, becomes the organizer of independent educational, cognitive, communicative, creative activity of pupils, he has opportunities to improve the learning process, develop the communicative competence of students, the holistic development of their personality.

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